

TWINNED
By Stars

D1.2 STAKEHOLDER ENGAGEMENT PLAN

**WPI STRENGTHENING AND SUSTAINABILITY OF
COOPERATION NETWORKS IN MARITIME AND COASTAL
TOURISM IN THE ORS**

TWINNEDBYSTARS

**UNLOCKING THE POTENTIAL OF INNOVATION,
CIRCULARITY, AND DIGITALIZATION FOR ACCELERATING
NEW MARINE-BASED ECOTOURISM, JOINT PRACTICES
AND BUSINESSES IN ORS**

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¹ PU= Public, CO=Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services), CL=Classified, as referred to in Commission Decision 2001/844/EC

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ACRONYMS & ABBREVIATIONS

ANEN	Asociación Nacional de Empresas Náuticas
AZ	Azores
BE	Belgium
CA	Canary Islands
CAP	European Common Agricultural Policy
CE	Consulta Europa
CMC	Clúster Marítimo de Canarias
CO	Project Coordinator
D	Deliverable
DG GROW	Directorate-General for Internal Market, Industry, Entrepreneurship and SMEs
EC	European Commission
EMFAF	European Maritime Fisheries and Aquaculture Fund
ES	Spain
EU	European Union
FR	France
GA	Grant Agreement
GDRP	General Data Protection Regulation
GVA	Gross Value Added
IN	International
JRC	Joint Research Centre
MAD	Madeira
MAR	Martinique
MARE	Directorate-General Maritime Affairs and Fisheries
MEPs	Members of the European Parliament
NACE	National Classification of Economic Activities
OECD	The Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development
ORs	Outermost Regions
PhD	Doctorate
PM ²	Project Management Methodology of the European Commission
PT	Portugal

QH	Quadruple Helix
R&D&I	Research and Development and Innovation
SMEs	Small and medium-sized enterprises
UNWTO	United Nations World Tourism Organization
VET	Vocational education and training
WP	Work Package

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

TWINNEDbySTARS aims at increasing the competitiveness of the maritime tourism sector in Outermost regions while contributing to protect marine biodiversity, preserving the cultural heritage and develop marine astro-tourism, recalling ancient navigators as a sustainable destination for these remote territories, by strengthening partnerships already in operation, capacity building and co-creation for tourism products.

One of the objectives of TWINNEDbySTARS is the implementation of an inclusive process, involving stakeholders at regional, national, and European level, giving priority to industry (the business sector that composes the nautical value and supply chain at the level of the participating regions), civil society (including sailors' and consumers' associations), public administrations (such as tourist boards), and academia.

This document details the stakeholder engagement plan that will be followed during the implementation of the TWINNEDbySTARS initiative. After a brief summary on maritime and coastal tourism in the EU, the objectives of the project, as well as the most relevant stakeholder engagement approaches (QH and multi-actor approach), the methodology followed for the identification and mapping of stakeholders is included, which is then followed by the engagement methodology describing the forms of engagement as well as the materials and actions of communication needed to support this plan, through standard communication rules and GDPR compliance.

INTRODUCTION

In 2006, the European Commission launched the pilot project "European Destinations of Excellence", with the aim of supporting European tourism by highlighting the diversity and unique characteristics shared by European tourist destinations, as well as promoting emerging tourist destinations and activities, **considering the social, cultural, and environmental sustainability of the territories.**

Coastal and maritime tourism encompasses a wide range of activities undertaken in the shoreline and the marine environments, where leisure, recreation are the main motivations for travelling. In this segment the tourist can carry out activities such as enjoying the beaches, sailing, diving, enjoy the coastal landscapes or the cultural offers at the destination (Lam-González et al., 2019).

EU coastal areas are amongst the most preferred tourist destinations for European and international travellers, making coastal and maritime tourism the biggest, growing sector of the EU Blue Economy in terms of GVA and employment. More than half of EU bed capacity is concentrated in regions with a sea border. For the economy of many non-landlocked EU Member States – especially in Southern Europe – tourism generates a significant portion of their total national revenue. At the same time, coastal regions are those with the highest seasonality, i.e., with tourism demand concentrated in a limited number of months, usually July and August. Aligning TWINNEDbySTARS with the statistical data published by the European Commission in its annual Blue Economy Report, the Coastal tourism sector comprises recreational activities taking place in proximity of the sea (e.g. beach-based tourism, coastal walks, wildlife watching) as well as those taking place in the maritime area, including nautical sports (e.g. sailing, scuba diving, cruising, etc.).

Spain led the Coastal tourism sector in terms of employment contributing with 20% of jobs, followed by Italy with 13%, Greece with 11% and France and Germany both with 10%. In terms of GVA, France led with 20%, followed by Spain with 16%, and Italy and Germany with 13% both.

Employment by Member State

Value Added by Member State

Figure 1. Share of employment and GVA in the EU Coastal tourism sector, 2020. Source: The EU blue economy report 2023.

In 2022 the European Commission's DG GROW launches the Transition pathway for tourism, this is a plan jointly created with actors of the tourism ecosystem detailing key actions, targets, and conditions to achieve the green and digital transitions and long-term resilience of the sector.

The transition pathway calls on the tourism community to implement measures in twenty-seven areas, including:

- To invest in circularity to reduce energy, waste, water, and pollution, and at the same time to better meet the increasing demand for sustainable tourism.
- To enhance data sharing practices to allow for new innovative tourism services and improve the sustainable management of destinations.
- To invest in skills to ensure the availability of qualified workforce and attractive careers in the ecosystem.

The competitiveness of the EU tourism industry will largely depend on its capacity to meet the need and customer demand to become more sustainable. A Eurobarometer survey from October 2021 indicated that 82% of Europeans are willing to **change their travel habits for more sustainable practices**, including consuming locally sourced products, reducing waste and water consumption, travelling off-season or to less visited destinations and choosing transport options based on their ecological impact. Their key interests in selecting destinations are nature (41%) and culture (42%), and a third would be ready to pay more to support local nature and local communities. Other surveys also show that 65% of travellers would be interested in engaging with authentic experiences related to local culture (social sustainability).

Coastal and maritime tourism actors should develop sustainable tourism in line with the new approach for the sustainable blue economy in the EU, European strategy for more growth and jobs in coastal and maritime tourism, and the EU mission on 'Restore our Ocean and Waters by 2030'.

Our case in TWINNEDbySTARS, as the most remote parts of the EU – the outermost regions (ORs) – are highly dependent on tourism as it accounts for a particularly high share of our economy (up to 35% of GDP). We suffer from seasonal fluctuations (the Canary Islands being an exception in the last few years) and are fully dependent on (limited) air connections.

The BiodivERsA Stakeholder Engagement Handbook (Durham et al. 2014) is one of the most comprehensive guides for stakeholder engagement in flagship R&D&I projects, so for TWINNEDbySTARS this manual is of great importance in the definition of this plan.

Establishing the reason(s) for engagement is a critical first step to take before any engagement is undertaken. Existing literature suggests that the benefits of engagement can far outweigh the risks, including those risks posed by lack of engagement. If well planned, and adequately resourced, successful engagement can enrich research and deliver better knowledge, and thus better outcomes.

Stakeholder engagement is a focal element of the TWINNEDbySTARS project, this initiative aims to keep stakeholders engaged throughout the different phases of the project and therefore focuses on a sustainable engagement. This approach is described in simple terms below:

- **Stakeholder engagement** can be described as a broad, inclusive, and continuous process and an open, constructive relationship between a project and those potentially affected

by or interested in it for a purpose to achieve accepted outcomes (Durham et al. 2014; AccountAbility, 2015).

- **Sustainable engagement** of stakeholders' places emphasis on engaging stakeholders in a long-term and meaningful way, or in other words, sustaining relationships and commitments (Israel et al. 2006).

Stakeholder engagement is about building relationships with them, thereby enhancing their trust, acceptance, and willingness to participate, investing time and commitment, and connecting with other stakeholders who can endorse the project. Through stakeholder engagement, concerns, expectations, interests, and opportunities can be explored from a variety of perspectives, and a wide range of perspectives and knowledge can be gathered. By incorporating a greater number and diversity of actors and their knowledge, TWINNEDbySTARS is driven to create on demand, sustainable and more equitable products, and activities, adapted to the local circumstances of the EU's ORs in the Atlantic.

THE PROJECT

TWINNEDbySTARS aims at converting European ORs into an internationally recognized maritime ecotourism destination, which exploit benefits of tourism for marine biodiversity conservation and climate change mitigation. The project builds on the success of previous projects in the Macaronesian region, which have built networks and methodological frameworks to co-design and tune up transformational marine eco-tourism products and activities, involving SMEs located on different islands. On-board marine environmental education, navigation, respectful sighting, and start light attributes are examples of good practices that combined with unpublished interpretative experiences of marine sighting have generated highly satisfactory tourist experiences and higher environmentally responsible behaviour of SMEs and tourists. TWINNEDbySTARS aims to scale out these experiences at the level of the EU ORs, while fostering the uptake of green and digital innovation by these communities, strengthening partnerships already in operation, capacity building, and opportunities for co-creation.

TWINNEDbySTARS builds upon the results of previous projects such as [NAUTICOM](#), an Interreg MAC project which led to the development of a new tourism product consisting of a one-week nautical experience for the sighting of marine fauna and pelagic birds across the most important natural reserves of Macaronesia and covering the islands of Madeira, Dessertas, Salvajes, the Chinijo Archipelago and Lanzarote.

The viability of our project hinges on the execution of tangible activities involving both public and private entities that collectively represent the quadruple helix of the concerned regions. The envisaged collaboration is well-founded, drawing on the established working relationships among many of the participating entities from prior projects. In the initial phase, encompassing the first half of the project duration, activities such as analysis, mapping, stakeholder engagement, co-creation, and training definition will be implemented. Subsequently, during the second half, the focus will shift towards training execution, implementation of the marketing and commercialization plan, and testing of the developed product.

THE CONSORTIUM

The TWINNEDbySTARS consortium has professionals with extensive experience in the nautical tourism sector, both in the applied and research fields, in business support through clusters and chambers of commerce, or in the regulation and promotion of activities of this type, such as in the public administration sector.

This Project builds upon a university & a research centre, regional governments from ORs, a maritime cluster, SMEs and a chamber of commerce, a marina, and an EU-wide boating association.

Table 1. TWINNEDbySTARS consortium.

Partner No.	Participant organisation name	Acronym	Country
1	Universidad de Las Palmas de Gran Canaria	ULPGC/TIDES	ES
1.1	Fundación Canaria Parque Científico Tecnológico de la ULPGC	FPCPT/ULPGC	ES
2	Consulta Europa Projects and Innovation	CE	ES
3	Asociación Cluster Marítimo de Canarias	CMC	ES
4	Océano de Experiencias SL	NAUTIC OCEAN	ES
5	Centro Tecnológico de Ciencias Marinas	CETECIMA	ES
6	Associação MarinaFunchal	MARINA FUNCHAL	PT
7	Associação Comercial E Industrial Do Funchal	ACIF-CCIM	PT
8	Secretaria Regional do Mar e das Pescas	DRPM AZORES	PT
9	Collectivité Territoriale de Martinique	CTM	FR
10	European Boating Industry	EBI	BE

THE WORK PACKAGE 1

The objectives of the WP1 are:

- Strengthening and sustainability of cooperation networks in maritime and coastal tourism in the ORs.
- Acting as a link between the quadruple helix representatives.
- Fostering the homogeneity of the network through the promotion of the certification (quality, tourism, environmental, Starlight...).

- Promoting the clustered participation in international fairs with the resulting product(s) within the "Trade Winds Starlight Adventure" and the promotion of a common brand image.

The tasks to be carried out to achieve these objectives are as follows:

T1.1. Analysis of existing cooperation networks in maritime and coastal tourism in the Atlantic ORs, mapping of actors in the quadruple helix and stakeholder engagement plan. Therefore, this report is included in this task.

T1.2. Homogenization and promotion of certification: enhancement of digitalization and circular economy.

T1.3. Elaboration and implementation of the internationalization and legacy plan.

THE QUADRUPLE HELIX APPROACH (QH)

TWINNEDbySTARS aims to carry out a capacity building programme in WP2 with tourism firms and other relevant stakeholders, to increase awareness, motivation, skills, and provide them with tools to accelerate digital and ecological transition, and to identify opportunities for open and innovation with actors from other ORs and in parallel in WP3 design and implementing the co-creation workshops on tourism products, applying the methodology for developing joint tourism product(s).

TWINNEDbySTARS will target representatives of the Quadruple Helix Model recognising four major actors in the innovation system: science, policy, industry, and society, being all four categories equally important for the project long-term success. The Quadruple Helix (QH) approach is grounded on the idea that innovation is the outcome of an interactive process involving different spheres of actors, each contributing according to its 'institutional' function in society.

Stakeholder engagement is the process of involving those who have an interest in, or may be impacted by, infrastructure projects/options. Stakeholders include government agencies, infrastructure users and the local community.

The participating stakeholders can belong to any sector of society and, although there are many different distributions of society into sectors, the following distinction is commonly used, which adapted to TWINNEDbySTARS would stand as follows: (1) *Citizens or civil society*, which includes citizens and associations such as NGOs, trade unions, professional associations, sports associations, sailors and customer's associations, etc ; (2) *Industry*, which includes both large and small companies, clusters, sectoral associations, business federations, investors and, in general, the entire private sector; (3) *Government*, public institutions and the entire public administration; and (4) *Academia*, which includes universities, research centres, think tanks and other scientific and technological organizations. The engagement of these four main sectors is commonly known as the "quadruple helix engagement approach".

Figure 2. The QH engagement approach adapted to the project. Source: CMC own production.

In the project, co-creation plays a very important role, for the actions of WP2 and WP3, this type of process converts hierarchical or vertical processes into collaborative and horizontal ones. In addition, it can be applied in any part of the process, from the capacity building process to the definition of the product, and from more abstract processes of conceptualization to more specific processes of definition and testing the product. By merging different people and thus different areas of specialization and experience, innovative results are generated from an interdisciplinary point of view – which would not be possible if each actor tackled the challenge on their own. This is the added value that co-creation provides when used with the quadruple helix approach.

THE MULTI-ACTOR APPROACH

The multi-actor approach is a way of conducting R&D&I in a responsible manner that aims to make the R&D&I process and its results more reliable, demand-driven, shared, and relevant to society. This involves more than just widely disseminating the results of a project or listening to the views of a committee of stakeholders.

The idea of this approach is to have the whole value chain of the products or services that are part of the project target represented, in the case of TWINNEDbySTARS we would be talking about the value chain of nautical activities which is included below.

Figure 3. Nautical value chain. Source: Diagnosis of the Nautical sports and leisure sub-sector and its capacities. SMARTBLUE and NAUTICOM projects. CMC own elaboration.

It is essentially about the end-users of the project results, supported by other useful intermediaries and actors who can provide further knowledge and innovative ideas relevant to the project objectives and support communication and dissemination.

In this type of approach, stakeholders must be involved throughout the project, from its conception and the partnership that makes it up (in our case we have representatives from all of them: government representatives, academia, industry - both from business associations and companies themselves - and civil society integrated in the participating non-profit associations).

Furthermore, this approach proposes that the basic elements of the project proposal come from both science and practice, considering the co-creation processes, which are also included as a relevant aspect in WP2 and WP3 of this initiative.

Ultimately, professionals and end-users as well as the value and supply chain will be involved not only as simple objects of study, but to leverage their practical and local knowledge and/or entrepreneurial skills to improve the quality of life of citizens. This will in parallel contribute to

and accelerate the acceptance and uptake of new ideas, approaches and solutions developed in the project.

This multi-actor approach has been working for many years in those R&D&I projects linked to the implementation of the European Common Agricultural Policy (CAP), being required in many of its funding lines, which can also be seen in the Horizon Europe Work program (2023-24) - Cluster 6. 9. Food, Bioeconomy, Natural Resources, Agriculture and Environment.

Figure 4. CARE4BIO WEBINAR. Natalia BRZEZINA. European Commission, DG AGRI Unit F2 Research, and Innovation. Power point presentation about the Multi-Actor Approach.

For projects that include this approach in Cluster 6. 9. Food, Bioeconomy, Natural Resources, Agriculture and Environment, these actors would be: i) researchers, ii) farmers / farmers' groups and associations, iii) foresters / foresters' groups and associations, iv) aquaculture producers, v) fishers / fishers' groups and associations, vi) advisors, vii) food and bioeconomy businesses, viii) other businesses, ix) consumer associations, x) local communities, xi) citizens, xii) civil society organizations including NGOs, and xiii) government representatives.

The success of many projects in co-creating products or services has been based on establishing long-term participatory processes (i.e. not just one-day conferences or workshops) to engage with stakeholders and potential end-users of the work. For example, several EU-funded multi-actor projects created farmer-led innovation networks, farmer innovation groups and made unique actions such as the appointment of innovation and technology ambassadors, so-called "Food Heroes" where farmers and project representatives were encouraged to come together to solve a particular societal challenge on farms in the Netherlands.

These multi-actor networks are not just about connecting, it is necessary to foster effective engagement within the network and some of the important factors in achieving this are:

- Encourage openness and understanding within the network, considering the specific context.
- Allowing time for face-to-face conversation between network participants.

- Allow sufficient time for informal interactions to develop into relationships.
- Recognise the value of field visits in getting people from different backgrounds to communicate and share their knowledge and understanding.

One aspect to consider is the fact that different stakeholders will respond to information in different ways. Particular attention needs to be paid to how innovative project solutions are communicated, for example, by selecting effective ways of sharing complex academic results with a wide range of professionals working in different situations and occupations. Undoubtedly, the charisma of the people who carry out this communication is key to driving or facilitating the innovation process. Knowledge and expertise on the subject are essential, as is a focus on co-creation and inclusion. It is therefore important to assess the benefits of any individual or organisation joining the initiative as a stakeholder, both from their perspective and what they can bring to the group. The [LIAISON](#) project identified the following advantages of participating in a project under the multi-actor's approach:

- Access to wide networks (of people and organisations).
- Introduction to other projects
- Engagement with a wide range of stakeholders across Europe (and globally)
- Benefiting from access to external funding, especially for smaller or less established organisations
- Access to support from other partners with the opportunity to acquire new knowledge, skills, and capacities.

TWINNEDbySTARS has a variety of partners who have worked together in previous proposals and many of them are already integrated in networks beyond the project such as the Macaronesian Marine-Maritime Alliance A3M and the NAUTICOM Network, integrating in this initiative new actors from other territories that broaden the range of action and give sustainability to these strategic alliances and networks.

Although the present plan will be based on the involvement of stakeholders under a QH approach, given the similarities of the proposal with the multi-actor approach used mainly in agriculture, but also incipiently in projects linked to the EMFAF as well as in the Horizon Europe Cluster 6, we will take into account the values provided by this approach in the development of the co-creation processes to be developed in WP2 and WP3.

1. MAPPING STAKEHOLDERS

Mapping is an important step in understanding who the key stakeholders are, which expertise they have, and where and how they can contribute to the project. The objective of a mapping exercise is to ensure that potential external experts who might have an interest or a stake in the project’s results have been identified. This will lead to a more efficient and targeted communication strategy and will ensure high quality contributions from the stakeholders.

A stakeholder mapping exercise was conducted to identify, map and structure the stakeholder roles and their specific interests, impact, benefits, and knowledge in such a way that each stakeholder will be engaged differently. The purpose of this stakeholder mapping was to make a logical categorization of stakeholders which require adapted approaches to engagement within TWINNEDbySTARS.

The purpose of this activity is to ensure that, as far as possible, all relevant stakeholders are identified and contacted.

Figure 5. Responsibilities within the stakeholder identification process. Source: CMC own elaboration.

The stakeholder mapping process is an integral task of the TWINNEDbySTARS project in which all partners of the initiative are involved. Under the coordination of the Canary Islands Maritime Cluster guiding the methodology to be followed and providing databases, the Marine Science Technology Centre oversees carrying out the mapping task which is integrated in the deliverable *D1.1 Analysis of existing cooperation networks in maritime and coastal tourism in the Atlantic ORs and mapping of actors in the quadruple helix*. This task is also participated by Consulta Europa in charge of design and communication, where they are in responsible for the definition and production of the different necessary visual elements and their dissemination through the contact

channels of the project, as well as the reception of the data from the surveys, taking care of the data management policy. All this under the vision and alignment with the co-creation processes that will be developed in WP2 and WP3 under the leadership of the TIDES Institute of the ULPGC, coordinator of the project and academic partner that provides the context and global perspective for the mapping, as well as the elaboration of the surveys and the development of the messages showing the benefits of being part of TWINNEDbySTARS.

The complete mapping to be integrated in deliverable D1.1. will have the following phases:

- A. Definition of the scope and index of contents of the map: type of agents, competencies, capacities, nautical sectors where they operate, geographical scope of action, etc.
- B. Identification of stakeholders (initial list).
- C. Simplified Mapping (confirmed listing with partners) + partners sent invitational questionnaire to their own contacts.
- D. Collection of information about stakeholders (Excel form + some information sheet).
- E. First draft of the deliverable ***Mapping of actors in the quadruple helix***
- F. Review and input
- G. Validation

1.1 MAPPING METHODOLOGY

Generalities to consider when identifying stakeholders: (1) many stakeholder groups could be included in more than one category, as we have seen in figure 2, these entities could be considered in the 'overlaps' areas between the circles; (2) a stakeholder map is not analytically exhaustive, but a tool that illustrates the range of stakeholders and helps to develop the engagement plan; (3) it is important not to exclude any stakeholder during this identification phase, even if relations with them are not good, we believe they will be against the actions or feel unwilling to commit themselves; (4) the stakeholder map will evolve as the engagement process goes on and we learn more about our stakeholders, this is why it is an iterative process throughout the project; and (5) as we engage with stakeholders we should also ask them who else they think we should engage with.

The identification of agents will be focused on entities that meet the following requirements:

- **Territorial:** Supra-regional, regional, and insular entities based in the ORs (Azores, Canary Islands, Madeira, and Martinique) of the Atlantic, and national, European, and international entities relevant to the theme of the TWINNEDbySTARS project.
- **Thematic:** That offer support services for nautical and tourism activities (marine activities, blue tourism, services to recreational and sport boats, astronomical observation, specialized tourist services, tourism diversification, promotion of cooperation in the marine-maritime field, etc.)
- **Sectorial:** Nautical in general or specialized in a specific one (marinas, tourism promotion, astronomical observation, sustainable tourism, etc.)

- **Type of entity:** Any type of entity: public or private, and legal personality (organizations, associations, foundations, commercial companies, etc.). The group of the quadruple helix to which the entity belongs shall be indicated.

The identification of stakeholders has been done based on the experience of the project partners and considering the actors of the quadruple helix. related to the ORs involved (Canary Islands – CA; Madeira – MAD; Azores – AZ; and Martinique – MAR), the countries to which they belong (ES, PT, FR) and the European (EU) or international level (IN), under the following categories:

- Academia (science stakeholders, research community, researchers, PhD students)
- Government (policy, and decision-makers, public administrations, authorities)
- Citizens or civil society (societal actors)
- Industry (nautical value and supply chain, as well as other representatives of active and experiential travel sector)

A description of the targeted stakeholder groups of TWINNEDbySTARS is provided below:

Table 2. Stakeholder groups description.

Stakeholder groups	Description
Government (Public administrations, authorities) Group 1	<p>Government or public institutions and the entire public administration are included in this category; however, we mainly refer to organisations at regional, national, and European level on tourism and on destination marketing.</p> <p>Policymakers at regional, national and EU level will be targeted. At EU level several Directorates-General will be reached (GROW, MARE), the JRC, the European Parliament (intergroups, committees, MEPs), international Ocean governance initiatives, OECD Ocean Economy working group and UNWTO.</p>
Industry Group 2	<p>This category of stakeholders is one of the most important for TWINNEDbySTARS and includes both large and small companies, clusters, sectoral associations, business federations, investors and, in general, the entire private sector.</p> <p>As this is the most extensive section, a dedicated table (table 3) has been prepared which includes the types of entities to be included in the group.</p>
Academia (Research education) Group 3	<p>Also called science stakeholders include a diverse network of actors managing, coordinating, or conducting scientific research related to tourism. This group includes the research community, science managers as well students and PhD scientists working on universities, research centres, think tanks and other scientific and technological organizations, also tourism schools and VET and high schools.</p>

Stakeholder groups	Description
	The academia category includes actors at local, national, intergovernmental, and European levels as well as representatives of other EU projects.
Citizens or civil society (NGOs) Group 4	This category includes citizens and associations such as NGOs, trade unions, professional associations, sports associations, sailors, and costumer’s associations, etc.

1.2 IDENTIFICATION OF STAKEHOLDERS

The Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC): “a person or an organisation that has a legitimate interest in a project or entity or would be affected by a particular action or policy” (Parry et al., 2007). With this definition, everyone involved in the project can be considered a stakeholder, including the project partners. However, when we refer to consortium members, we will generally use the term “project partner” or “consortium partners”, while stakeholder will be reserved for individuals external to the consortium.

For the project, the most important stakeholders, are the business entities, so the objective is to involve them at the highest level of integration. To define the entities that are part of the industry category we have based on the European NACE Rev.2 distribution used by (1) the Spanish National Association of Nautical Companies (ANEN) and the Complutense University of Madrid (UCM) in the study *Impacto Económico de la Náutica de Recreo*, (2) the categorisation described in the European IMPACTOUR project, (3) as well as the previous work carried out in the initiative financed by the INTERREG MAC programme called SMART BLUEF (MAC 2/2.3d/355), in which several of the TWINNEDbySTARS partners took part:

Table 3. Entities that are part of the industry category.

SUBSECTOR	SEGMENT
Ports and marinas	Private Nautical port managers Port services concessions
Services to recreational and sport boats	Repair and maintenance workshops Mechanics Radio electronics Nautical refrigeration Dry docks and winter storage Fuel supply Inspection

SUBSECTOR	SEGMENT
Manufacture and sale and purchase of recreational and sport vessels	Boat manufacturing Boat distributors Official services Accessories and supplies
Charter and maritime excursions	Nautical charter Maritime excursions Whale watching Fishing tourism and marine tourism
Coastal tourism and water sports activities	Scuba diving Snorkelling Freediving Open water swimming Sailing / foil sports: surfing, windsurfing, kitesurfing, and similar Light boat activities: rowing, canoeing, and kayaking
Services to coastal tourism and water sports activities	Sale and/or rental of equipment accessories for sailing, surfing, windsurfing, and kitesurfing activities Sale and/or rental of accessories and equipment for rowing, canoeing and kayaking activities. Sale and/or rental of accessories and equipment for recreational underwater activities: scuba diving and snorkelling.
Nautical training and qualifications	Academies Clubs Sport schools
Commercial services	Tour Operators Travel agencies
Investors	Investors
Active and experiential tourism	Active tourism SMEs Experiential travel SMEs
Business associations	Tourism and maritime clusters Tourism associations Regional business federations

SUBSECTOR	SEGMENT
	Chambers of commerce
Investors	Investors
Media	Regional, national, and European media Digital media

For the elaboration of the TWINNEDbySTARS stakeholder database the partners were asked to explore among their contacts to identify those who could be involved in the project as a stakeholder. To comply with GDPR regulations, the next step was for each partner to send an email to these pre-selected contacts with information about the project including the benefits of participating in TWINNEDbySTARS and to complete a simple survey agreeing to be contacted at later stages of the project. Similarly, for stakeholder mapping, the project partners were asked to research various regional databases mainly for the detection of business associations, companies, and civil society. All this information will be included in an Excel file which also contains the contact details and the categorisation of the stakeholder according to 4 main groups (government, academia, industry, and civil society).

The process of stakeholder identification and engagement is an iterative and continuous process throughout the life of the project. Furthermore, if it is detected that there is a significant lack of participation of representatives of any group and/or region, the efforts of the partners will be focused on bridging this gap, and project partners will have the opportunity to propose new contacts at various stages of the project.

The full list of variables recorded for each stakeholder are listed below. The rich detail in the stakeholder pool will facilitate efficient targeting of stakeholders for the appropriate stakeholder engagement context.

- Region / Island
- Name of the entity
- Sector Quadruple Helix / Subsector
- Contact person
 - Direct email
 - General email
 - Phone number
 - Web / social media
- Other (observations etc.)
- Partner in contact
- Previous project

In addition, deliverable D 1.1. will have a detailed fact sheet for the most relevant stakeholders, which will include only public data.

Table 4. Fact sheet template for the most relevant stakeholders.

Name of the entity		Logo	
Business name			
Entity Type			
Sector of quadruple helix	Group 1 / Group 2 / Group 3 / Group 4		
Type of activity / services			
Other relevant information			
Contact Details*	Address		
	Phone number		
	Mail		
Informational Resources	Web		
	Social media	Facebook	
		Instagram	
		Twitter	
		LinkedIn	

**Contact details with public access, complying with data protection regulations.*

Finally, we will have two main databases linked to the stakeholders: (1) an excel table of mapping entities in which only public data will be included and (2) an excel table with the data of those entities/individuals who have responded to the EU survey and have accepted to be contacted in later phases of the project. These two databases will be available to all project partners in the internal document repository.

2. ENGAGEMENT OF STAKEHOLDERS

The feasibility of the TWINNEDbySTARS project relies on the realisation of concrete activities with the involvement of both public and private entities representing the quadruple helix of the involved regions. The proposed collaboration has a solid base, as many of the entities have worked together in previous projects.

One of the objectives of TWINNEDbySTARS is the implementation of an inclusive process, involving stakeholders at regional, national, and European level, giving priority to industry (the business sector that composes the nautical value and supply chain at the level of the participating regions), civil society (including sailors' and consumers' associations), public administrations (such as tourist boards), and academia.

Although the implementation of the engagement will be established more in detail during the WP execution, it is foreseen that in WP2 each type of stakeholder will have a specific role, for example the entities integrated in the groups of representatives of academia, government and civil society will be involved mainly in actions such as support to the design of self-diagnosis tools and evaluation of results, participation in focus groups for validation of the questionnaire to the companies, taking part in questionnaires on how they perceive the coastal and maritime tourism sector in terms of circular economy and digitization and where progress should be prioritized, participation in meetings with companies for the transmission of data and personal experiences, as mentors or trainers.

As for the industry representatives and mainly SMEs, the main beneficiaries of the actions of this WP, they will be integrated in a business hub, where work will be done at a:

1. motivational and data collection with rewards to involve them in the following steps.
2. self-diagnosis to know their needs and current situation in circular economy, digitalization, and innovation.
3. sharing results, individual recommendations and data and good practices in open sessions.
4. participate in building a shared vision on the project intervention priorities for improvement.
5. designing tailor-made training or mentoring courses.
6. spaces for networking and work exchanges for personal growth and internationalization.

Regarding WP3, industry (SMEs) will participate mainly through matchmaking events and co-creation workshops to identify ideas and joint business models, with the rest of the groups (academia, government, and civil society) having a role more linked to the evaluation of the best business ideas to be supported by the project using criteria pre-established by the working team.

2.1 TYPE AND DEGREE OF STAKEHOLDER ENGAGEMENT

Managing project stakeholders is a critical project management activity that begins in the Initiating Phase of the project, and ends in the Closing Phase, when stakeholders' overall project experience and satisfaction are evaluated.

According to PM² (project management methodology of the European Commission) the steps to involve stakeholders in a project are as follows:

1. Analyse the expectations, attitudes, level of interest and influence of key project stakeholders. Beware of stakeholders who are less than enthusiastic or opposed to the project.
2. Devise communication and management strategies that encourage stakeholders to get involved and contribute.
3. Continually monitor stakeholder reactions or changing attitudes and manage accordingly.
4. Ensure that any planned stakeholder management activities are time-bound and focused. Keep in mind that the contribution/involvement of various stakeholders may be different in each project phase.
5. Align the Communications Management Plan with Stakeholder Management needs, particularly in the areas of project acceptance, transition, and business implementation.

Before planning starts, a stakeholder analysis must be established to identify and prioritise the main stakeholders to be involved in TWINNEDbySTARS.

The key steps of the analysis are summarised below:

1. **Stakeholder identification:** they were asked to explore among their contacts to identify those who could be involved in the project as a stakeholder. Similarly, for stakeholder mapping, they were asked to research various regional databases mainly for the detection of business associations, companies, and civil society. All this information is included in an Excel file which also contains the contact details and the categorisation of the stakeholder according to 4 main groups (government, academia, industry, and civil society).
2. **Prioritisation of stakeholders:** once the database is available, they are prioritised according to table 5, according to their level of influence and interest.
3. **Stakeholder understanding:** Finally, the partners were asked to review the prioritisation done in the previous phase, to reflect their interest in the project, what information they are most interested in and who influences the project the most.

Table 5. Stakeholder prioritisation table based on the matrix between influence and interest. The BiodivERsA Stakeholder Engagement Handbook. Durham E., et al (2014).

Prioritization (according to interest and influence)	
Inform (-influence -interest)	Monitor these stakeholders and keep them adequately updated as and when required , tailoring communications to meet stakeholders needs
Consult (-influence +interest)	Provide these stakeholders with enough information and interaction to keep them updated and to address their concerns , but do not overwhelm them with too much information
Involve (+influence -interest)	Keep these stakeholders adequately informed and maintain regular contact to ensure no major issues are arising

Prioritization (according to interest and influence)	
Collaborate (+influence +interest)	These stakeholders are essential to the project and must be fully engaged with . Enlist their full help, create partnerships, galvanize support of the project, and make the greatest effort to keep them satisfied

Figure 6. Stakeholder prioritisation matrix for TWINNEDbySTARS project. Source: CMC own elaboration.

For the project, the most important stakeholders, due to the co-creation process that will be established in both WP2 capacity building and WP3 for the generation of the new product, are (1) the business entities, so the objective is to involve them at the highest level of integration, as collaborators and (2) civil society, which includes associations such as NGOs, trade unions,

professional associations, sports associations, sailors and costumer's associations, etc. as they are the target audience of the product.

2.2 OVERALL APPROACH TO STAKEHOLDER ENGAGEMENT

A centralised stakeholder engagement will ensure that the stakeholders are involved in a focused and efficient way with mutual benefits. Furthermore, it will ensure that the project is adhering to appropriate rules for privacy policy and ethics in personal data management.

In the field of innovation, maintaining the commitment of a wider group of stakeholders in the projects can be difficult, in the case of TWINNEDbySTARS the challenge lies in including companies, which in the nautical sector are mostly micro-enterprises with a high workload during the high tourist season, taking into account that for example in Spain there are around 3.700 companies with activity in this sector, taking into account the directory carried out by the National Association of Nautical Companies (ANEN) and the Complutense University of Madrid (UCM) in the study "Economic Impact of Nautical Companies in Spain".

This can be alleviated if their participation is planned from the beginning, because early engagement is likely to make the engagement process more credible and relevant; and finding the right mix of participants and ensuring no groups have been excluded will enhance legitimacy and credibility (CRELE approach, Durham E., et al (2014)).

However, there are certain factors that may limit the ability of some stakeholders to participate, contribute and benefit from a co-creation activity. Organising more interactive "seeing is believing" activities such as study groups, field visits, roundtables and open events can help to engage and create links. Either because of barriers, or independently from them, the *lack of trust, motivation or interest* in the project can become a major obstacle of the engagement process.

It is important once they are engaged, to remember that the public wants to know that their voices mean something and that the time they have invested has made a difference and has had an impact. Participants should always be kept informed about the stage of the project implementation they are stepping into, so they can provide appropriate input. This also helps to manage expectations around how much the community can affect the outcome.

Although there is strong evidence that effective engagement can bring many benefits to the research processes linked to co-creation, it is important to approach engagement critically, and be aware of some of the challenges and limitations that may be faced, because for example some stakeholders may lack the time to engage, or experience '*stakeholder fatigue*', that is they begin to feel overloaded with engagement activities, which negatively affects willingness to participate and lessens the quality of their input. In addition, unbalanced engagement can lead to perverse or poor decisions if it inadvertently reinforces existing privileges, or where group dynamics discourage minority perspectives from being expressed.

Intangible benefits need to be explained/commented during the first contacts. For TWINNEDbySTARS these benefits include:

Why join TWINNEDbySTARS?

Join a diverse network of companies in Macaronesia for collaboration opportunities.

Get involved in the development of new goods that will allow you to internationalise your particular offerings and products while also expanding your company's reach by targeting new segments that value ecotourism.

Improve your company's competitiveness by learning from our analysis and training courses. This will help you improve existing goods and establish new ones.

Access to the main resources to carry out the most effective marketing strategies and to additional materials.

Enhance your company's sustainability strategy and its offerings with TWINNED by STARS support.

Have access to different companies products and offerings, enabling vertical integration through partnerships and synergies.

Join a single story among participating companies to strengthen the Macaronesia destination for mutual benefit.

Learn how to integrate the experiences and offerings of various astrotourism and ecotourism products.

Be part of our tourism community!

www.twinnedbystars.eu

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Figure 7. benefits of being part of TWINNEDbySTARS. Source: CE own elaboration.

The tools and methods of stakeholder engagement include processes already familiar to the industry stakeholders (our more important group) such as market research surveys and focus groups, opinion leader research, conferences, and workshops. Other, less familiar participation

processes and facilitation techniques may also be useful; tools and techniques developed by practitioners in international development, public planning, democratic participation, and online communities can be especially helpful in consensus building and problem solving with diverse groups of stakeholders.

It is important to apply the engagement technique best suited to a given stakeholder, given the differences in the stakeholder groups and stakeholder types. There are three relevant criteria to assess the appropriate engagement technique used for a given stakeholder or stakeholder group:

- The level of interest of the stakeholder group in participating in the project
- The level of influence of the stakeholder group on the project
- The appropriate engagement and knowledge consultation methods

When it is clear which stakeholders you aim to engage, it is time to identify the engagement benefits or why it would be interesting for them to engage with the project. Communicating tailored elements that may spark their interest increases the likelihood of the stakeholders answering the call to action.

Figure 8. Levels of engagement versus engagement channels from a nuclear perspective. Source: Own elaboration.

Figure 8 shows the overview of this approach, where from a core point of view, in the centre are the entities that will have a higher level of participation in the project and the green channels of involvement, coinciding with the group of business-related stakeholders, which being the core part will be in smaller numbers than the rest of the concentric rings with a lower level of

involvement and their relations with the rest of the stakeholder groups, namely civil society, academia and governmental entities.

Identifying engagement benefits for our stakeholders is based on the *role* they are asked to play and the stakeholder *group* they are part of. Tailored communication of benefits can be made by combining benefits from the stakeholder roles with benefits from the stakeholder groups. Additionally, sectoral motivations a stakeholder might have in relation to the project can be included to further tailor the communication.

When it is planned to engage the same group of stakeholders for a longer period, it is possible to consider generating additional stakeholder benefits for them. For example, organizing activities that are not necessarily related to our product such as a webinar to learn about a topic, a reception, an excursion to learn about the area, issues, local products, etc. These extras may contribute to the motivation of stakeholders to stay engaged. Such informal exchanges can help to get to know each other better and support building a trust relationship.

2.3 ENGAGEMENT CHANNELS

In the proposal phase, the project team has identified a series of engagement channels, through actions included mainly in WP5 Dissemination & Communication, that include physical meetings and digital tools which will facilitate stakeholder participation in consultation and mutual learning process.

Stakeholder engagement methods can be participatory (two-way) or informative (one-way). Informative methods are considered for engagement if they meet the needs of stakeholders and are designed with those needs in mind, which usually means that they are co-defined and possibly co-designed with the stakeholders.

Below there is a suggestion of potential actions that can be developed in the project. All these channels and actions will depend on the interest and availability of the people involved in the project.

As stated in the BiodivERsA HandBook, the intensity of the interaction with stakeholders will be delimited according to the type of stakeholder and the importance of them for the development of WP2 and WP3.

Firstly, stakeholders will be consulted mainly by email by all project partners, initially to their internal contacts and in a second phase to those new contacts that emerge from the mapping phase (described in section 1. MAPPING STAKEHOLDERS). In this first communication the identified stakeholder will be invited to fill in a first survey in which general data of the person and the entity he/she represents will be collected, and consents to use their data in the project, after that the industry representatives will be invited by email to complete a second survey asking for more specific data related to their business model in order to detect their potential motivation to participate more intensively in the WP2 and WP3 actions. These surveys will be made available online using the [EU Survey application](#).

To complement the feedback from the surveys, dissemination actions are foreseen throughout the project, mainly included in WP5, but also in WP2 and WP3 during the co-creation phases. The actions to be carried out will be varied, during which the stakeholder engagement plan will be

implemented through interviews, focus groups, webinars, technical workshops, and matchmaking actions. Depending on the actions included in the above mentioned WP2 (capacity building), WP3 (product development) and WP5 (dissemination and communication) the approach will be at different levels:

- **Informative participation** (knowledge dissemination): according to the actions included in WP5, mainly the project's newsletters, website, and social networks.
- **Consultative participation** (knowledge utilisation): the same as above, but including for these, other survey phases and considering their participation in open forums and co-creation workshops for the design of WP2 and WP3 actions.
- **Involved participation** (knowledge utilisation in the design phases of the co-creation processes by maintaining regular contact): through the WP5 dissemination channels, but also considering their participation in co-creation workshops for the design of WP2 and WP3 actions, and policy recommendations. Also, if necessary, through bilateral meetings and interviews.
- **Collaborative participation** (where stakeholders will be directly involved in the co-creation and implementation of actions): participating also as beneficiaries of capacity building actions, product definition and implementation, steering and advisory groups, and by including them in multi-stakeholder alliances, partnerships, voluntary initiatives, and joint projects.

Figure 9. Engagement channels and their associated level of engagement from a cumulative perspective.
Source: CMC own elaboration.

2.4 STANDARDIZED RULES FOR CONTACTING STAKEHOLDERS

As part of stakeholder engagement activities, the consortium might promote the project on open-access stakeholder platforms or working groups, as well as contacts publicly available on institutional websites.

Stakeholders and, overall, the public will be reached by digital communication and dissemination activities as planned in WP5 e.g., through website's promotion, social media posts and campaigns, publication of releases on local press, promotion of newsletters, sharing of project promotional videos, sharing of promotional materials, etc. Stakeholders will be able to subscribe to the project newsletter in a dedicated form published on the TWINNEDbySTARS website and will be receiving periodic newsletters from the project. They will be able to unsubscribe at any time if they wanted, in line with the project Data Management Plan and GDPR rules.

Also, the direct approach to stakeholders will take place via email, through three phases described below and shown in Figure 10. These three phases will be carried out iteratively during the life of the project as new stakeholders are identified or to address imbalances in the participation of any of the proposed stakeholder groups.

Figure 10. Three phases of contact via email. Source: Own elaboration.

- **First email**
This is the first contact with stakeholders by this channel. A standard communication is sent giving information about TIWINNEDbySTARS, indicating the advantages of being involved in this initiative as a stakeholder and inviting them to complete an EU Survey. The contacts will be those selected from the databases of each partner, plus those identified in public databases after a first mapping phase. In parallel the partners will feed the Excel stakeholder data including only public data.
- **Complete de survey and GDRP consent**
The survey to be completed requests contact information as well as informs and asks for consent to share their data with TWINNEDbySTARS partners to be contacted in the future and, apart from receiving the project newsletter, to participate in project actions such as: Co-creation workshops (design); Co-authorship of Policy recommendations; One-to-one meetings and interviews; Questionnaires and surveys; Open forums; among others.

Clarify that this specific consent will be included to ask interested participants if they consent to be included in the newsletter subscribers and re-contacted for future events organised by the project.

- **Second email**

This email is sent specifically to SMEs or business associations to fill in a second EU Survey in order to have more information about them and involve in the highest level of involvement in which they will be able to participate and/or benefit from actions such as field visits; social events; be beneficiaries of capacity building actions; intervene in the product definition and implementation; form part of steering and advisory groups; trade fair participation; practical demonstrations; including them in multi-stakeholder alliances; among others.

As a direct measure in this second EU Survey form, just for responding to it, SMEs or business associations will get one masterclass about keys to boost sales through digital campaigns or one pill course about the benefits of astronomical observations in a nautical experience.

On the other hand, in the specific case of organisation of project events, webinars, and conferences, the activities with stakeholders will be promoted by all consortium partners among their channels to maximise reach-out. For events, an official invitation letter, an agenda, and a registration form will be shared to allow people sign up to project activities.

2.5 COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION ACTIVITY

Communication and dissemination are crucial for the development of the stakeholder engagement plan, so during the design and implementation phases of the plan, it will be fully aligned with the TWINNEDbySTARS Dissemination and Communication Plan. In particular, actions to attract and involve stakeholders will be designed with a strong involvement of the communication and dissemination team, which will elaborate graphic and visual elements in order to reach out to the different target groups.

This paragraph presents a set of five principles upon which the TWINNEDbySTARS Dissemination and Communication Plan has been built:

- **Adaptability:** Given the scope of the project and the specific themes involved, the communication and dissemination activities need to be adaptable to the project's various research themes, stakeholder communities and project progress. For example, specific channels are to be used to reach target groups, and dissemination materials may have to be tailored to the needs of different end users.
- **Flexibility:** Communication needs to be flexible and open to create a responsive framework to changing needs and challenges.
- **Tailoring of messages/usage of appropriate language:** TWINNEDbySTARS needs to be able to speak to a variety of actors and stakeholders with different background and objectives in mind. To achieve this, the project must formulate key messages tailored to the needs and expectations of the various target audiences, and expressed in appropriate

language (specialised, technical communication vs. plain, jargon-free communication using laymen’s language).

- **Exploitation of synergies:** To maximize impact and efficiency of exploitation an extensive network of external collaborations of project partners will be used, and opportunities sought to join and contribute to existing networks and platforms which have relevant remits.
- **Gender sensitive and inclusive communication:** Certain words and images we use to communicate must be considered carefully since they can perpetuate images of socially prescribed gender roles and behaviours. TWINNEDbySTARS will adopt a non-hierarchical and nonpatronizing style, to promote gender-sensitive communication, identify gender stereotypes and use a fair and balanced representation of women and men in communication.

Furthermore, as a transversal principle in the communication actions to involve stakeholders, it is important for the TWINNEDbySTARS partners to reflect in these visual elements and messages the diversity of the territories of the EU ORs involved in the project, as well as the heterogeneity of the target audience of the final product to be designed and tested in this initiative.

Communication and dissemination activities in TWINNEDbySTARS will aim thus at ensuring visibility of the project but also at triggering effective interactions with stakeholders at the many project’s interfaces.

In Table 6, the communication channels and type of information to be shared with each stakeholder is defined:

Table 6. Target groups communication details.

TARGET GROUP	COMMUNICATION CHANNELS	TYPE OF INFORMATION
Academia (Science stakeholders)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Open-access publications • Conference presentations • Social media and website • Trainings / workshops • Journals • Specialised and scientific media 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Project description and updates • Project scientific publications • Project results
Government (Policy makers)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Joint sessions/events • Seminars, roundtables, etc • Newsletter • Media (press releases) • Policy feedback reports 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Project results • Project description and updates • Project impact • Advantages of the prototype
Industry	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Events and trainings / workshops • (Social) Media and direct emailing • Website • Synergies • Factsheets • Promotional material 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Project results • Business/exploitation plan

TARGET GROUP	COMMUNICATION CHANNELS	TYPE OF INFORMATION
Civil society (Society/public)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Website and newsletter (Social) Media Focus groups Webinars Promotional materials and factsheets 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Project description and updates Project publications Project impact assessment

An effective strategy of D&C should adapt its key messages to each type of audience/stakeholder targeted to achieve the maximum impact and engagement. At the same time, each project outputs should be appropriately channelled to achieve their highest exploitation levels. The Table 7 tailors the D&C and engagement activities to each type of stakeholder.

Table 7. Tailored D&C and engagement activities to each type of stakeholder.

TYPE OF STAKEHOLDER	D&C ACTIVITIES	ENGAGEMENT ACTIVITIES
Science stakeholders (Academia)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Deliverables Shorter research briefs might be produced Prepare posters to be shared at scientific conferences Webinars Trainings Peer review publication Zenodo community 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Propose participation in webinars to present on specific topics Workshops/focus groups
Policy makers (Government)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Preparation of policy briefs from the deliverables Webinars National & International Conferences held for end users and policy makers Policy briefs in national languages 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Webinars to get inputs to shape project activities and expected results Video interviews Workshop/roundtables
Industry	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> National conferences / events Specific type of events (visits to installations, exhibitions) Briefs and factsheets by e-mail, through newsletters and social media Promotional videos 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Video interviews to promote their activities Focus groups Webinars Conferences
Society/public (Civil society)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> National conferences /events Social media Leaflets Videos Specific type of events 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Webinars Round-tables Discussions Focus groups

2.6 STAKEHOLDERS ENGAGEMENT MATERIALS

Several online and offline promotional materials have been customized to enhance stakeholder engagement with the project's activities. This material includes brochures, flyers, posters, presentations, newsletters, social media posts, videos, and websites designed to communicate key messages, benefits, and objectives to stakeholders. The goal of these materials is to raise awareness, generate interest, and encourage stakeholders to support or participate in TWINNEDbySTARS' activities. Regarding the online promotion of the project, official TWINNEDbySTARS social media channels were created, from which CE regularly publishes content tagged strategically to attract the project's targeted stakeholders over time. Accounts in [Instagram](#), [Facebook](#), [LinkedIn](#) and [X](#) are available since the beginning of the project.

These are some examples of promotional materials tailored to reach stakeholders:

ONLINE

- Online posters:

- Advertising for the stakeholders to enrol in the project activities and fill in the EU survey:

Co-funded by the European Union

- Banner web:

OFFLINE

- Printed posters and roll up:

- Printed brochures (6 pages):

What is TWINNEDbySTARS about?

TWINNEDbySTARS aims to make the outermost regions more visible and well-known in the tourism industry. These regions play a crucial role in supporting EU environmental policies. The project will showcase the innovative potential of tourism in these regions, focusing on aspects like marine biodiversity, cultural heritage, and astrotourism. This will involve creating networks and frameworks for collaborative design and development of a unique marine ecotourism experience centred around navigation and stargazing.

Objectives:

- Strengthening and sustaining cooperation networks in maritime and coastal tourism within the ORs. This involves linking the quadruple helix and ensuring network homogeneity through the promotion of certifications and promoting a unified brand image.
- Upskilling and capacity building for tourism firms and stakeholders in coastal and maritime tourism (circular economy practices, digital transition, networking and innovation).
- Creating new spaces for the co-creation of innovative products and nautical tourism experiences (star tourism, marine ecotourism, sustainable Atlantic crossing using trade winds, and the application of virtual reality).

Grant agreement number: 101124900

Granting authority: European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency

Starting date: 1 October 2023

Project duration: 36 months

Funding rate: 85%

Grant amount: 996,630.11 €

www.twinnedbystars.eu

Methodology:

The viability of the project hinges on the execution of tangible activities involving both public and private entities that collectively represent the quadruple helix of the concerned regions. The envisaged collaboration is well-founded, drawing on the established working relationships among many of the participating entities from prior projects.

In the initial phase, activities such as analysis, mapping, stakeholder engagement, co-creation, and training definition will be implemented. Subsequently, the focus will shift towards training execution, implementation of the marketing and commercialisation plan, and testing of the developed product.

REVIEW AND IMPROVE

We apply a learning-by-doing approach for stakeholder engagement. Evaluation is an indispensable step to make sure we are on the right track and to incorporate a feedback circuit and regular reflection on our stakeholder engagement. To evaluate our tailored engagement approach, we will collect feedback from the engaged stakeholders and self-reflect after the main engagement activities to assess whether we need to adjust our approach for future engagement activities.

Furthermore, although this plan is delivered in the M6 as described in the GA, it is a living document and may be subject to improvements because of the implementation and evaluation stages of the stakeholder engagement actions.

REFERENCES

- Bueno, E., & Quesada, M. (2023).** D1.3 AquaWind Stakeholder Engagement Plan. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8158886>
- Durham E., Baker H., Smith M., Moore E. & Morgan V. (2014).** The BiodivERsA Stakeholder Engagement Handbook. BiodivERsA, Paris (108 pp).
- Eleonore Lehn, & Marianne Gros. (2021).** D6.1: Coordination strategy for stakeholders' engagement. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6759041>
- European Commission,** Directorate-General for Digital Services, PM², Project management methodology – Guide 3.0, Publications Office of the European Union, 2018, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2799/755246>
- European Commission,** Directorate-General for Internal Market, Industry, Entrepreneurship and SMEs, (2022). Transition pathway for tourism, Publications Office of the European Union. <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/products-statistical-reports/w/ks-ft-22-011>
- European Commission,** EUROSTAT (2023). Tourism Satellite Accounts in Europe 2023 edition. <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2873/344425>
- European Commission,** Directorate-General for Maritime Affairs and Fisheries, Joint Research Centre, Borriello, A., Calvo Santos, A., Ghiani, M. (2023). The EU blue economy report 2023, Publications Office of the European Union. <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2771/7151>
- European Commission.** Directorate-General for Agriculture and Rural Development. Directorate C – CAP Strategic Plans II. Unit D.1 – Rural areas and networks. Guidelines for data on European Innovation Partnership (EIP) Operational Groups Programming period 2023-2027. Version 3.0 (2023-10-17). EIP-AGRI common format (The EIP-AGRI common format for Horizon multi-actor projects 2021-2027 at the time of writing this deliverable was not yet published.). Source: https://eu-cap-network.ec.europa.eu/projects_en
- European Commission.** BRUSSELS DECLARATION ON A EUROPEAN NETWORK OF DESTINATIONS OF EXCELLENCE FOR SUSTAINABLE TOURISM. Ares(2015)5822556 - 14/12/2015. https://single-market-economy.ec.europa.eu/sectors/tourism/awards-and-outreach-activities/eden_en
- Fani Galatsopoulou (Dr), & Clio Kenterelidou (Dr). (2020).** Water Sports Tourism Education Stakeholders Map. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8183771>
- García Álvarez, J.; Aliaga de Migule, H.; Charouni, L (2021),** Stakeholders' engagement plan. IMPACTOUR project Deliverable 3.2. <https://www.impactour.eu/system/files/2021-11/D3.2%20-%20IMPACTOUR%20Stakeholders%27%20Engagement%20Plan%20-%20vFinal.pdf>
- Helen Aldis, Ana Allamand, & Simone Osborn. (2022).** Logrando un impacto: Guía Práctica. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6521882>
- Helen Aldis, Ana Allamand, & Simone Osborn. (2022).** Trabajando en equipo: Guía Práctica. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6521863>
- Helen Aldis, Ana Allamand, & Simone Osborn. (2022).** Buena planificación: Guía Práctica. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6521868>

Helen Aldis, Ana Allamand, & Simone Osborn. (2022). Asociaciones saludables: Guía Práctica. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6521872>

Helen Aldis, Ana Allamand, & Simone Osborn. (2022). Asociaciones conectadas: Guía Práctica. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6521876>

Heussaff, C. (2022). IAM_COMPACT_D2.1_Stakeholder_Engagement_Plan. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10430887>

Hong, L., Lüthje, M., Björn, E., & Miettinen, S. (2023). Fostering stakeholder engagement in sustainable cultural tourism development in nature-based sites: A case study on using methodological layering of art-based methods. En *The Routledge Handbook of Nature-Based Tourism Development* (pp. 183-200). Taylor & Francis. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781003230748-15>

Horizon Europe Work program (2023-24) - Cluster 6. 9. Food, Bioeconomy, Natural Resources, Agriculture and Environment. European Commission Decision C(2023) 2178 of 31 March 2023. Pag. 21 – 23. https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/horizon/wp-call/2023-2024/wp-9-food-bioeconomy-natural-resources-agriculture-and-environment_horizon-2023-2024_en.pdf

Israel BA, Krieger J, Vlahov D, Ciske S, Foley M, Fortin P, ... Palermo A. (2006). Challenges and facilitating factors in sustaining community-based participatory research partnerships: Lessons learned from the Detroit, New York City and Seattle Urban Research Centers. *Journal of Urban Health*; 83:1022–1040. <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s11524-006-9110-1>

Leone, M., Lammens, L., & Julie, C. (2023). INTERLACE Stakeholder Engagement Strategy (D1.5). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10473713>

Matozinhos, K., Magalhães, J., Arias, R., & Guasch, B. (2022). The ENJOI Engagement Methodology for target users and quadruple helix stakeholders (v1.5). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7472845>

Molina M. & Bueno, E. (2018). Diagnóstico del Subsector de la Náutica y sus capacidades. Deliverable of the SMARTBLUE and NAUTICOM projects.

NAUCAMExperience: <https://www.naucamexperience.com/es/que-es-naucamexperience/>

NAUTICOM project (MAC/2.3d/158), from INTERREG MAC Program, cofounded by FEDER funds. Website: <https://www.proyectonauticom.com/>

Novales, A. et al (2018). Impacto Económico de la Náutica de Recreo. Asociación Nacional de Empresas Náuticas (ANEN) y Universidad Complutense de Madrid (UCM). https://www.ucm.es/data/cont/media/www/pag-36703/FullReportICAE_ANEN.pdf

Parry, M.L., et al., Eds. (2007) *Climate Change 2007: Impacts, Adaptation and Vulnerability, Contribution of Working Group II to the Fourth Assessment Report of IPCC*, Cambridge University Press, Cambridge. https://www.ipcc.ch/site/assets/uploads/2018/03/ar4_wg2_full_report.pdf

Perello, M., & Avagnina, B. (2018). D3.1 - Guidelines for stakeholders' identification and engagement within the RHHs. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6340166>

Scheme source from Interreg Europe, RELOS3 project “From Regional to Local: Successful deployment of the Smart Specialization Strategies”, website: <https://www.interregeurope.eu/project/events/te2-quadruple-helix-sustainability>.

Smart Altitude “Alpine winter tourism territories demonstrating an integrated framework for a low-carbon, high-impact and resilient future”. Interreg Alpine Space program. WP T3 Smart Altitude Toolkit. Activity A.T3.3 Stakeholder engagement plan for attractive low carbon territories. D.T3.3.1 Report on territorial stakeholder engagement. (2020). <https://www.alpine-space.eu/project/smart-altitude/>

SMART BLUEF project (MAC 2/2.3d/355), from INTERREG MAC Program, cofounded by FEDER funds. Website: <https://www.smartblueproject.com/>

Szemző, H, Tönkö, A, Turai, E (2021). Deliverable D 1.2. Stakeholder Engagement Plan. <https://textour-project.eu/>

The Stakeholder Engagement Manual. Volume 2: The Practitioner's Handbook on Stakeholder Engagement. AccountAbility, United Nations Environment Programme, Stakeholder Research Associates Canada Inc. ISBN 1 901693 220. First Edition October 2005.

Yen E. Lam-González, Carmelo J. León, Javier de León (2019). Assessing the effects of the climatic satisfaction on nautical tourists' on-site activities and expenditure decisions, Journal of Destination Marketing & Management, Volume 14, 100372, ISSN 2212-571X, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jdmm.2019.100372>.

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